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MUNDARIJA

ПРИНЦИПЫ ПЕРЕХОДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ, СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ	12
Набиев Дилмурод Хамидуллаевич	
YaSHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLASH TIRISH TA'SIRIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TRANSFORMASIYASI	19
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xo'jaevich	
РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ТРУДА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЕГО ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ	26
Гулямов Саидахор Саидахмедович, Икрамов Мурат Акрамович, Очилов Акрам Одилевич	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASH MAQSADIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT"GA O'TISH ZARURATI	33
O.X. Hamidov, D.Sh. Yavmutov	
ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ КАК ФАКТОР УСИЛЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	38
Татьяна Юрьевна Анопченко, Сергей Вадимович Ревунов, Роман Вадимович Ревунов	
TRANSITION OF RUSSIAN REGIONS TO A CLOSED-LOOP ECONOMY	49
Nikonov Sergey Mikhailovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Filipenko Alexander Alexandrovich	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA TUZILISHI	53
Navruz-Zoda Baxtiyor Negmatovich	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК ДРАЙВЕР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА И МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	59
Зокирова Нодира Каландаровна	
KREATIV IQTISODIYOT VA UNING INDUSTRIYA TURLARINING NAZARIY MASALALARI	64
Mamayunus Pardaev, Obid Pardaev, Akram Ochilov	
EKOLOGIK OMILLARNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHDA ERISHISH	73
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o'g'li	
INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI KOOPERASIYASINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	81
Rahmatulla Ergashev	
KARTOSHKA MOSLANUVCHAN NAVLARI TURLI EKISH MUDDATLARI VA MULCHALASHLARDA HOSILDORLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	86
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Toshpulatova Surayyo Tulqin qizi, Ismayilov Alisher Isroilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHNING KALITI	90
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ» В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	93
Сайёра Насимовна Хамраева	
SABZAVOT (SHIRIN) MAKKAJO'XORI AJRATILGAN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV-DURAGAYLARINI ASOSIY VA TAKRORIY EKINLAR SIFATIDA TURLI MUDDATLARDA YETISHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	97
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Nurillaev Ilhom Xolbek o'g'li, Jabborov Botir Shukurovich	
ZAMONAVIY BOZOR MUNOSABATLARIDA SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY JIHATLARI	101
Ivatov Irisbek	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	105
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich, Abdiyeva Flora Botir qizi	
GREEN ECONOMY: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE AND UZBEKISTAN'S PATH	110
Dilmurod Mirza-Akhmedovich Rasulev, Dildorakhon Ulugbek kizi Shomuradova	

OLIV TA'LIM XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TARG'IB QILISH BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	113
Musayev Bekjon Shukurillayevich	
TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BARQAROR STRATEGIK RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN USULLAR TAHLILI	116
Turdibekov Xasan Ibragimovich	
ЗЕЛЁНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ФАКТОРЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	120
Орипов Ильхом Абдуллаевич	
Перспективы развития цифровой трансформации в Республике Узбекистан	128
Мусабеков Джорабек Хакимджанович, Воронин Сергей Александрович	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	133
G.Erkayeva	
Barqaror ish o'rinlarini yaratishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'рни	138
Qo'chqorov G'aybulla Fayzullayevich, Qo'ziyeva Shaxnoza Bozor qizi	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	141
Фазлитдин Бахадирович Аминов	
RESPUBLIKADA EKOLOGIK TOZA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISH ASOSIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISH	145
Q. J. Mirzayev, F. F. Ulug'murodov	
Qoraqalpog'istonda sanoatni restruktizatsiyalash va yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish: muammolar, istiqbollar va statistik tahlillar	150
Abipova Gulmira Salavatdinovna	
CHORVACHILIK XO'JALIKLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AGLOMERATSIYANING AHAMIYATI.....	153
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA STRATEGIYASINING KOMPANIYA UCHUN AHAMIYATI.....	156
Ergashev Toxir Kurbanovich, Toxirova Nigora Zokirjon qizi	
CHORVACHILIK KLASSTERLARI VA AGLOMERATSION RIVOJLANISH: O'ZARO TA'SIR VA SYNERGIYALAR	161
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
HUDUDLARNING INNOVATSIYON SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH	165
J.A. Ismatullayev, A. Do'lanov	
СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	171
Нафасов Тохиржон, Г. П. Эркаева	
Mamlakatimizda ishsizlikni kamaytirishga qaratilgan islohotlar.....	174
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich	
USE OF THE ADVANCED EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF FARMING AND HOUSEHOLDS	178
Ochilova Nargiza Akramovna	
SHAHAR AGLOMERATSIYALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	181
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
IQTISODIY O'SISHDA MEHNAT MIGRATSIYASINING AHAMIYATI.....	184
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Saidakbarov Jamshid Ne'matullo o'g'li	
TURIZMNIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	189
Qosimov Jahongir	
РЫНОК ГОСТИНИЧНЫХ УСЛУГ В ТУРИЗМЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДИВЕРСИФИКАЦИИ И ДЕМОКРАТИЗАЦИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ	192
Ташмаматов Садирдин Нажмиддинович	

O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KADRLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISHDA DUAL TA'LIMDAN FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISH	196
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Xamidova Mo'tabarxon Abdumalik qizi	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA AUTSORSING XIZMATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	201
Nasiba Ergasheva	
KORXONALARDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI	207
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Nurullayeva Vazira O'ktamovna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И РИСКИ	211
Номазов Бахром Бобомуродович	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ESG В ФИНАНСОВУЮ СФЕРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	215
Алимова Азиза Шерзатовна	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON MANAGEMENT	219
Ergashev Tokhir Kurbanovich, Tohirova Nigora Zokirjon kizi	
O'ZBEKISTONNING "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT STRATEGIYASI" NI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	224
Ergasheva Nazira Muratovna, Soyibov Mirjon Bekjonovich	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УСЛУГ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ И КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ	227
Алимова Муниса Юлчиевна	
РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБУВНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ.....	232
Расулов Нозимжон Набиджонович	
AGLOMERATSIYA VA IQTISODIY O'SISH: SABAB-OQIBAT ALOQASI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	236
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
KORXONALARNING SOLIQ IDORALARIDA HISOBGA OLINISHIDAN HOSIL BO'LGAN ORTIQCHA TO'LOVLARINI BOJXONA TO'LOVLARIDA HISOBGA OLISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	239
Boykabilov Bahodir Mustafaevich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARGA INVESTITSIYALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	242
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA "IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN AGROKOOPERATIV" TASHKIL ETISH ORQALI TA'MINOT ZANJIRI BOSHQARUVINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	248
Amirqulov Shuxrat Olimovich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING MOLIYAVIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	254
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
TURIZMNING MADANIY-TARIXIY RESURSLARI: ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR VA TAMOYILLAR	258
Ruzmanov Dilshod Usmanovich	
BARQAROR TURIZM DESTINATSIYALARINING SIG'IMINI VAHOLASH METODIKASI.....	262
Ibroximov Nodirbek Xasanovich	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ ЭНЕРГИИ КАК ОСНОВА ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	266
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ МАРКЕТИНГ И ПОВЕДЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ.....	272
Раимова Муборак Джураевна	
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" NING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI	276
Djumayev Asqar Xaydarovich	

RAQAMLI MARKETINGNING ISTE'MOLCHI XULQ-ATVORIGA TA'SIRI.....	281
Raimova Muborak Jurayevna, Dilmurodov O'tkir	
HUDUDNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI	287
SH.A. Buriyev	
SAVDO XIZMATLARINING ASOSIY FAOLIYAT KO'RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINI BAHOLASH.....	291
Muxamedova Aziza Ravshanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI: YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQLIM O'ZGARISHINI YENGISHDAGI O'RNI VA GLOBAL HAMKORLIK.....	295
Usmonov Murodjon Xolmurod o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМА НАЛОГОВОГО АДМИНИСТРИРОВАНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	299
Абдулов Дамир Рустамович	
О'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH ISTIQBOLLARI	305
Yuldashev Shamsiddin Qiyamiddinovich, Boliyeva Baxora Farxodovna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА: КОНЦЕПЦИИ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ.....	308
Туляганова Шахноза Самукджановна	
О'ТА ERTAGI TARVUZNING HIMOYALANGAN JOYLAR UCHUN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV VA DURAGAYLARINI AJRATISH, ULARNI TURLI O'G'IT ME'YORLARIDA HOSILDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	311
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Amirov Xamidulla Suyunovich, Umirova Durdona Muqum qizi	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ОТРАСЛИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	315
Уралов Элшод, Вельм М.В.	
DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY AS A MODEL OF PROGRESS IN HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	320
Abdiev Alimardon	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СЕКТОРА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ И РАЗВИТИЯ КАДРОВОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА.....	322
Мухаммадбобур Салимов	
КИЧИК BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	326
Suyunov Jabbor Mahmudovich	
“SALOHİYAT” TUSHUNCHASINING MAZMUNI VA IQTISODIY-IJTIMOIIY MOHIYATI.....	331
Zoirov G'olibjon Toshtemir o'g'li	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUVIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI	334
Salimov Muhammadbobur Qodir o'g'li	
O'QUV JARAYONLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	337
Tilakov Sherzod	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING XALQARO TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI.....	340
Sattarov Umirzoq, Ro'ziev Zafar Ikromovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT XOM ASHYOLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	343
Xazratov Sarvar Ibragimovich	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	348
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, O'rinov Diyorbek Xolmo'min o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI O'QUV MARKAZLARI VA KURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	353
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	

SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRARISH VA SOTISH SIFATI HAMDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	357
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Ziyodullayeva Marjona Alisher qizi	
OMMAVIY TADBIRLAR YORDAMIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: O'ZBEKISTON VA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	360
Ibragimov Sardorbek Xusanovich	
Анализ цифровой трансформации и её влияния на привлечение инвестиций в регионы Узбекистана.....	365
Рахмонова Дурдона Хасан кизи	
Korxonada moliyaviy salohiyatini baholashning statistik tahlili.....	370
M.O. Musurmonova	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE BANKING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Kadirov Lutfulla Khalimovich	
PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR SOLUTION.....	381
Sharopov Temirmalik Rustam o'g'li	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ORQALI QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOAT KOMPLEKSINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	385
U.Shukurov	
FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES	390
Hazratkulov Shahboz Boboqul ogli	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA TA'LIMNING ROLI.....	394
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHI UCHUN DAVLAT TOMONIDAN YARATILAYOTGAN IMKONIYATLAR.....	398
Xudoyorov Azizbek Avaz o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI YAXSHILASHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	404
Safarov Sh. S.	
IJTIMOYIY MENEJMENTDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	408
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Davronova Farangiz	
«ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ФИНАНСОВЫЙ КОНТРОЛЬ: КАЗНАЧЕЙСКИЙ КОНТРОЛЬ В БЮДЖЕТНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ».....	415
Файзуллаева Зилола Равшановна, Д.Х. Пулатов	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING ASOSIY JIHATLARI.....	421
Urozoza Shaxlo Hasan qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	427
Safarov Shoxrux Sattor o'g'li	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	431
Alimardonova Gulfizoda Alimardon kizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR HISOBINI TO'G'RI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	434
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	441
Berdimurodova Farzona Bahodir qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING BIZNES VA IQTISODIYOTDAGI ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	446
Davronova Farangiz Ilhom qizi	

ZAMONAVIY RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA PUL VA BANK TIZIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ISTIQBOLLARI HAMDA AHAMIYATI	452
Axtamova Ozoda Ulug'bek qizi, Cho'liyeva Gulsanam Yulchi qizi, G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI: TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	460
N. Qo'ziboyeva	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ZARURATI.....	466
Vayskulov Ramazon Alisher o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA TURIZM KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA IQTISODIY INTEGRATSIYA.....	470
Xushvaqto'v Ramziddin	
ILMIY SALOHİYAT VA OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINING UZVIY BOG'LIQLIGI: TAHLIL VA TAVSIYALAR	476
Muratov A'zam Alisher o'g'li, Ochilov Akram Odilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: GREEN CREDIT.....	480
Eshtemirova Ma'rifat Akram qizi, Kabilova Shaxnoza Jurayevna	
DEHQON XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI NARXLARINING DINAMIKASI VA BOZOR MUVOZANATI MODELLARINI QO'RISH.	483
Ergashov Yashnarbek Istamovich	
The Role of Renewable Energy in the Green Economy.....	488
Khudoyberdiyeva Olima, Yakhshikulova Mokhinur	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish: asosiy muammolar va imkoniyatlar	494
Jumanazarov Asilbek Utkirbek o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQOBAT USTUNLIGI ORQALI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH OMILLARI	498
Ro'ziqulov Jamshid Ulug'bek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SIYOSATINING ZAMONAVIY TRENDLARI HAMDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	504
Shodiyev Jahongir	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	509
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna, Sh. S. Sa'dullayev	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASIDA MAHSULOTLAR INTENSIV RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH JARAYONLARI	512
Saburov Jumanazar Salievich	
SUG'URTA XIZMATLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI.....	516
E.Sobirov	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”GA O'TISH ORQALI TABIIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING ATROF-MUHITGA SALBIY TA'SIRINI KAMAYTIRISH	520
Xo'janova Gulshoda Otamurodovna	
QISHLOQ JOYLARDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL YO'NALISHLARI	526
Dilafroz Taylakova	
KORXONALARDA EKOLOGIK INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI TAHLILI.....	532
Ulashov Aliboy Rashid o'g'li	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BANK VA MOLIYAVIY TIZIMLAR UCHUN YANGI IMKONIYATLAR TAHLILI HAMDA KELGUSIDAGI ISTIQBOLLARI	538
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Alarov Asilbek Oybek o'g'li	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIGI VA EKOLOGIK IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH MASALALARI.....	545
O'rinov Diyor, Xolliyev Sh.B.	

YASHIL IQTISODOYOT VA UNDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	549
Erminov Elbek Erkin o'g'li, Yaxshiqulova Moxinur Toxir qizi	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA KADRLARNING TUTGAN O'RNI	553
Turayeva Nargiza Rustamovna	
IQTISODIYOTDA TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	557
G.P.Erkayeva, N.H.Qo'ziboyeva	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING AHAMIYATI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH STRATEGIYASI	560
Samadova Jasmina Sherali qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
"YASHIL" ENERGETIKA VA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT.....	564
Qarshiyeva Dilsora Ismoil qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
MAMLAKAT BUDJETINING SHAKLLANISHI VA DAROMADLAR TAQSIMOTINING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI	569
Ashirqulova Sevinch Sarvar qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	574
Urozoza Shahlo Hasan qizi, Rahmonova Tillaoy Malik qizi	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHINING KO'RSATGICHLARI.....	579
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	583
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Mirzayev Azzamjon Jonuzokovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	588
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
СТРАТЕГИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ И ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭПОХУ НООНОМИКИ.....	593
Чекулаева Кристина	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИ ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	599
Чекулаева Кристина	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – MAMLAKAT TARAQQIYOTINING ASOSIY OMILI.....	605
Oybek Hamdamov, Qosimov Jahongir	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INSON KAPITALI SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI	608
M.Ostanova, Ro'ziyev Ramshid	
MODERN LEGAL BASIS FOR THE EFFICIENT USE OF FINANCIAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN OUR COUNTRY	613
Ismoilova Gulrux, Khayriddinov Shukhrat Botirovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA TABIIY - IQTISODIY MANBAALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	617
Mavlonov Shaxzod Shahobiddin o'g'li, Mavlonova Surayyo Xasan qizi	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA SOHALARNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI	621
Gulrux Arslon qizi Ismoilova, Shuxrat Xayriddinov Botirovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini bozorga yetkazishda transport xarajatlarini optimallashtirish yo'llari	625
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
Ziyorat turizmi obyektlaridan foydalanishda "Halol" standartlar bo'yicha baholash.....	629
Zaripov Toxirjon Yusufboy o'g'li	
O'zbekiston sug'urta bozori infratuzilmasini takomillashtirish.....	633
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni taminlashda davlat budjetining ahamiyatini oshirish yo'llari.....	637
Sheraliyev Nurbek Jumanazarovich	

TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDITLASH JARAYONI VA KREDITLASH AMALIYOTI TAHLILI	640
Sultonova Sevara Faxriddinovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARI MISOLIDA MILLIY MOLIYA BOZORINING SHAKLLANISHI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	643
Samadov Temur Oybek o'g'li	
AN'ANAVIY KURASH VA DYUZDO: TEXNIK VA FALSAFIY JIHATDAN TAQQOSLAMA TAHLIL	647
Tangriyev Abdullo Tovashovich	
DIGITAL SECURITY AND CYBER THREAT FACTORS IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY	650
Olimov Davron Olimovich	
JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTI SIYOSATINING RIVOJLANAYOTGAN DAVLATLAR IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI.....	653
Jalolov Umidjon Xudoyberdi o'g'li, Yegamberdiyev Shuxrat Satimbayevich	
РАЗВИТИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ФИНАНСОВОГО КОНТРОЛЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	657
Турсунбоева Нилуфар Отабековна	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI.....	659
Faxriddinov Bahriddin	
AGROLOGISTIKA TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHNING AGROEKSPORT SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	663
Faxriddinov Bahriddin	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY SIYOSATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA INSON KAPITALI VA IJTIMOY SALOHIYATNING O'RNI	667
Zoirov G'olibjon Toshtemir o'g'li	
XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNING O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA TA'SIRI.....	670
Srajidinova Nodira Shavkatovna	
STRESS-TESTLASH AMALIYOTI VA UNING TIJORAT BANKLARI BARQARORLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDAGI ROLI.....	675
Abdusalamov Olimjon Eshmirzayevich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDATURIZM SOHASIGA INVESTITSİYALAR KIRITILISH HOLATI VA SOHADAGI O'ZGARISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	679
Salomov Farrux Komil o'g'li, Hasanova Parvina	
“AKADEMIK KO'NIKMA VA KASBIY KOMPETENSIYA” FANIDA MUSTAQIL TA'LIMNING PEDAGOGIK MODELLARI: ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TAHLIL VA TAKLIFLAR	683
Doniyorova Gulnoza Anvar qizi	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI INSON KAPITALINI MUSTAHKAMLASH.....	688
Oripova Madinabonu Mansur qizi	
REKLAMADA RANG VA PSIXOLOGIYA	691
Muxtorxonova Ozoda Axror qizi	
GO'SHT VA SUT ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI RIVOJLANITIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	694
Qurbonov Alisher Boboqulovich, Abdullaev Jasur Jabborovich	
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR INVENTORY AUDIT AND CONTROL	699
Nigora Alimkhanova	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПЕРСОНАЛИЗАЦИИ, ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ	703
Камалова Малика Низамовна, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITINI VAHOLASHDA TAHLILY USULLARNING AHAMIYATI	708
Alimxanova Nigora Alimxanovna	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ И УСЛОВИЯ ПЕРЕХОДА К ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: АНАЛИЗ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ОПЫТА И ИХ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	712
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	

TRANSFORMATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION: MODERN APPROACHES AND CHALLENGES.....	717
Yuldasheva Makhliyo Bakhtiyar qizi	
QISHLOQ HUDUDLARI IJTIMOY INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBALARI VA O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	723
M.Yu.Alimova, Rustamova Gavhar Baxtiyarovna	
HR-MENEJMENT SIFATINING TEKSTIL KORXONALARIDA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI.....	726
Yormatov Ilmidin Toshmatovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA GLOBAL IMKONIYATLAR VA RAQAMLI HAMKORLIK.....	731
Salomov Farrux Komil o'g'li	
AUDIT NATIJALARINING SOLIQ TEKSHIRUVLARIGA TA'SIRI	736
Bakirov Norbek Norquchqor o'g'li	
OPTIMIZING GRADUATE ENROLLMENT MANAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	741
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	
FACTORS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF PRIVATE BUSINESS ENTITIES AND PRINCIPLES ENSURING THEIR SUSTAINABLE OPERATION.....	745
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Alimova Munisa Yulchiyevna	

FACTORS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF PRIVATE BUSINESS ENTITIES AND PRINCIPLES ENSURING THEIR SUSTAINABLE OPERATION

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Abstract: In the article, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on entrepreneurship adopted by the state in recent years, the decisions of the government on activating the activities of the Republican Coordinating Council for the development and promotion of entrepreneurship, the new procedure for microcrediting, and the simplification of licensing, registration, accounting, reporting, and taxation have significantly improved the economic environment for the activities and development of small businesses in the country, and existing problems, suggestions, and recommendations are presented.

Key words: modernization, private entrepreneurship, entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, efficiency, small business, national product.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada so'nggi yillarda davlat tomonidan qabul qilingan tadbirkorlikka oid qonunlar, respublikada tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish va qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha Respublika Muvofiqlashtiruvchi kengashi faoliyatini faollashtirishga qaratilgan Hukumat qarorlari, mikrokreditlashning yangi tartibi, litsenziyalash, ro'yxatdan o'tkazish, buxgalteriya hisobi, hisobot tuzish va soliqqa tortish jarayonlarining soddalashtirilishi mamlakatda kichik biznes faoliyati va rivojlanishi uchun iqtisodiy muhitni sezilarli darajada yaxshilagan tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, mavjud muammolar, taklif va tavsiyalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: modernizatsiya, xususiy tadbirkorlik, tadbirkor, tadbirkorlik, samaradorlik, kichik biznes, yalpi mahsulot.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются законы Республики Узбекистан о предпринимательской деятельности, принятые государством в последние годы, решения правительства, направленные на активизацию деятельности Республиканского координационного совета по развитию и поддержке предпринимательства, новый порядок микрокредитования, а также упрощение процедур лицензирования, регистрации, бухгалтерского учета, отчетности и налогообложения. Все эти изменения существенно улучшили экономическую среду для функционирования и развития малого бизнеса в стране. В работе также представлены существующие проблемы, предложения и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: модернизация, частное предпринимательство, предприниматель, предпринимательство, эффективность, малый бизнес, валовой продукт.

INTRODUCTION

The current stage of economic reforms in Uzbekistan is characterized by the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, granting it broad economic freedoms. Giving small business entities independence further increases their sense of responsibility for the final results of their activities. The development of small business and private entrepreneurship is one of the most important priority areas of economic reforms in Uzbekistan.

In this regard, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted in his address to the Oliy Majlis, “In general, entrepreneurship is a financial... In order to continue the work on supporting the family entrepreneurship program, 6 trillion soums in preferential loans will be allocated next year¹” – It’s not for nothing that this was emphasized. Small business entities are based on the principles of personal interest, initiative, and property responsibility in business management, as well as the development of various forms of property in the economy on the basis of equality and healthy competition. Small business entities fully comply with the principles of a market economy due to the fact that they own the products they produce, independently dispose of their property, financial and material resources, and have a strong sense of ownership.

Given the potential of small businesses to solve the country’s employment problem, ensure market saturation, and increase the competitiveness of the economy, special attention is being paid to the development of this sector.

In our opinion, this attention stems from the following specific characteristics of small businesses, namely:

- the ability to quickly adapt to market demand and produce quality products;
- the ability to meet the demand for goods and services necessary for the needs of the population in a relatively short period of time;
- relatively small initial investment;
- the opportunity to quickly create new jobs and help solve the employment problem;
- direct participation of the business owner (entrepreneur) in carrying out his/her tasks.

Currently, this sector is taking a leading position not only in accelerating the growth rates of the economy but also in solving issues of employment and increasing the income of the population, which are extremely important for our country. This is largely achieved due to the serious attention paid to strengthening the legal framework and forming a system of stable conditions, privileges, and credits for this sector of the economy. The current stage of economic reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan is characterized by the development of small business and granting it broad economic freedom. Giving small business entities independence makes them feel responsible for the final results of their activities.

Our scientific observations show that in recent years, a number of measures have been carried out in our country to develop small entrepreneurship: the wholesale and retail trade system has been reformed; an effective system of providing services to small businesses by infrastructure units is being created; a system for protecting the legitimate rights and interests of small businesses and guaranteeing freedom of entrepreneurship is being formed; a simplified and transparent procedure for registering entrepreneurs in the State Register has been introduced; favorable conditions have been created for entrepreneurs to freely purchase material and technical resources through stock exchanges; mandatory standardization and certification of products of manufacturing enterprises have been simplified; measures have been taken to reduce and simplify the tax burden; a shortened form of statistical and tax reporting has been introduced; the foreign economic activity of small businesses has been liberalized; a new system of initial capital formation and other forms of financial support for start-up entrepreneurs has been introduced, etc.

According to statistical data, as a result of the work carried out to support small businesses and protect the rights and interests of entrepreneurs, this sector of the economy is becoming increasingly strong, and its role in the economy of our republic — its contribution to employment and production — is increasing year by year. As of January 1, 2021, the contribution of small businesses to GDP was 53.9 percent. The contribution of small businesses to product output by economic sectors was 19.9 percent in industry, 16.1 percent in agriculture, 37.8 percent in trade, 6.4 percent in construction, and 54.9 percent in services².

In our opinion, in order to effectively address these problems in the field of small business development, it is necessary to develop and implement strategic programs of the republican government aimed at supporting this sector. The basis of such a concept should be structural changes that will eliminate imbalances and allow for more effective use of the economic potential of the regions.

In our opinion, the concept of small business development should focus primarily on supporting small business entities with economic potential, creating favorable opportunities for the development of sectors that are necessary for the industry and the region but are low-profit, encouraging economic structures that operate in accordance with the directions and goals of the republic’s socio-economic policy, establishing tax incentives for small enterprises producing products of regional importance, expanding leasing services and the investment risk insurance system, and providing conditions that allow small businesses with limited financial capabilities to use bank loans.

In our republic, banks are providing loans to support small businesses and private entrepreneurs. (Table 2)

1 Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis December 29, 2020

2 Data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Table 1. Loans granted by commercial banks to small businesses³ (billion soums)

Name of the regions	In 2024	In 2025	Compared to last year, in percent
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1,063.2	1,718.6	161.6
Andijan region	1,747.9	2,457.7	140.6
Bukhara region	1,966.0	3,286.9	167.2
Jizzakh region	976.5	2,644.3	270.8
Kashkadarya region	1 185.0	2,775.4	234.2
Navoi region	1,011.3	2,330.5	230.4
Namangan region	1 111.4	2,936.1	264.2
Samarkand region	2,507.7	4,392.3	175.1
Surkhandarya region	1 152.0	2,570.4	223.1
Syrdarya region	640.3	2,483.9	387.9
Tashkent region	1,954.0	3,425.0	175.3
Fergana region	1,977.5	3 227.5	163.2
Khorezm region	1,520.0	2 275.2	149.7
Tashkent city	11,836.0	18,906.4	159.7
Total	30,648.8	55,430.0	180.9

As can be seen from the table, if we analyze the amount of loans allocated by commercial banks to small businesses, loans provided across the republic increased by 80.9% in one year.⁴

As can be seen from the table, if we analyze the amount of preferential loans allocated in 2023-2024 within the framework of social programs aimed at developing family entrepreneurship, loans provided across the republic increased by 176.1% in one year⁵.

Table 2. Preferential loans allocated in 2024-2025 as part of social programs aimed at developing family entrepreneurship⁶ (billion soums)

Name of the regions	In 2024	In 2025	Compared to last year, in percent
Republic of Karakalpakstan	177.8	397.0	223.3
Andijan region	344.7	584.1	169.5
Bukhara region	201.6	422.5	209.6
Jizzakh region	165.8	405.5	244.5
Kashkadarya region	192.3	652.9	339.4
Navoi region	195.6	511.5	261.5
Namangan region	281.4	991.2	352.2
Samarkand region	233.7	587.8	251.5
Surkhandarya region	183.6	551.2	300.2
Syrdarya region	95.8	468.2	488.8
Tashkent region	112.0	556.4	497.0
Fergana region	266.5	707.7	265.5
Khorezm region	239.0	421.9	176.5
Tashkent city	49.1	303.1	617.0
Total	2,739.0	7,560.9	276.1

3 Report on the activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

4 Republic of Uzbekistan report on the activities of the central bank.

5 Republic of Uzbekistan Central bank activity report

6 Report on the activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan

This made it possible to ensure their social and legal protection. The total number of citizens registered as personal assistants and those engaged in cattle breeding on peasant farms exceeded one million.

At the new stage of economic reforms underway in Uzbekistan, the tasks of finding additional reserves to increase the efficiency of the economic mechanism and creating conditions that will allow the country to enter the world community are becoming increasingly important. The methods of economic recovery that are favorable for Uzbekistan are primarily based on the need to develop entrepreneurial activity.

One of the most important issues of the economic reforms being carried out by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to sharply increase the country's gross domestic product through small businesses and private entrepreneurship, solve employment issues, increase population incomes, and ensure national well-being. Because small businesses and private entrepreneurship, which require less investment than large production facilities and are more flexible, are able to quickly adapt to unstable market conditions and economic crises, modernize production, and remain resilient in the face of periodically recurring economic crises.

It is worth noting that as a result of the implementation of measures to improve the macroeconomic and business environment, positive developments have occurred in the development of small business in recent years. Its rapid development in the future will remain one of the priority tasks of implementing economic reforms. It is impossible to achieve sustainable economic growth and solve social problems without ensuring the rapid development of small and private entrepreneurship.

Over the past period, a number of legislative acts have been adopted by the state in order to support this sector of the economy. The adopted decrees and resolutions have played a significant role in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. These documents, in turn, are being amended and expanded every year in accordance with real needs. All this is aimed at ensuring the growth, free and extensive activity of small businesses and private entrepreneurs, as well as their support.

This means that the scale of support for small businesses in our republic is no less than that of foreign countries.

Our scientific analysis shows that, to date, state support for small businesses in our country has been implemented mainly in the following areas:

- the necessary legal and regulatory framework for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship has been created;
- priorities have been set for the development of small businesses, and a program to support small businesses and private entrepreneurship has been developed and is being implemented;
- a market infrastructure that helps small businesses grow has been established;
- preferential taxes, subsidies, preferential loans from state and extra-budgetary funds, and the attraction of loans from international financial institutions stimulate the development of small businesses;
- a mechanism for providing microloans to legal entities and individuals in foreign and national currencies has been developed and is being implemented.

The country has all the necessary conditions for the effective development of entrepreneurship. An organizational and legal framework for the priority development of foreign business has been created, and market infrastructure institutions have been formed; the banking and financial system is being improved, and the foreign exchange market is being liberalized. The country's favorable geographical location, labor resources, and the availability of mining, natural, and other resources allow for a wide range of economic activities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study demonstrates that small business and private entrepreneurship remain one of the key drivers of economic modernization, employment generation, and income growth in Uzbekistan. The analysis reveals that comprehensive reforms—such as the simplification of licensing and registration procedures, improvements in taxation, expansion of microcrediting mechanisms, and enhancements in market infrastructure—have significantly strengthened the institutional and economic foundations for the sustainable operation of small business entities. As a result, the contribution of small businesses to GDP, employment, and sectoral production continues to grow steadily. State support measures, including preferential loans, subsidies, investment incentives, and the formation of a favorable business environment, have accelerated the development of entrepreneurship across the regions. The sharp increase in bank lending to small businesses and the substantial rise in family entrepreneurship financing confirm the growing policy attention toward this sector. Nevertheless, the analysis indicates that further structural improvements are required to enhance the competitiveness and efficiency of private business entities in the long term.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to ensure sustainable development and strengthen the economic potential of small business entities in Uzbekistan:

1. Develop long-term national programs aimed at supporting small business and private entrepreneurship, taking into account regional economic potential and sector-specific needs.
 2. Reduce existing structural imbalances by promoting industries that are strategically important yet low-profit, ensuring their access to financial and institutional support.
 3. Enhance tax and financial incentives for small enterprises producing socially and regionally important goods, including expanding access to leasing and investment risk insurance services.
 4. Improve access to financing by expanding microcrediting, increasing preferential loan limits, and creating tailored lending instruments for start-up entrepreneurs and rural households.
 5. Strengthen the legal and regulatory framework by regularly updating entrepreneurial legislation based on international experience and the evolving needs of the domestic market.
 6. Develop modern market infrastructure, including business support centers, consulting services, innovation hubs, and digital platforms that facilitate entrepreneurship development.
 7. Increase the efficiency of public administration by simplifying reporting procedures, reducing bureaucratic barriers, and ensuring transparent monitoring of state support programs.
 8. Promote human capital development through entrepreneurship training programs, mentorship networks, and cooperation between universities, banks, and private enterprises.
- Implementing these recommendations will help further expand the private sector's contribution to GDP, enhance employment opportunities, and strengthen the competitiveness of Uzbekistan's national economy.

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